

MANAGERIAL COMPETENCE AND SUPERVISORY SKILLS OF PRINCIPALS IN CATHOLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN EASTERN VISAYAS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 20

Issue 1

Pages: 81-100

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1844

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11223333

Manuscript Accepted: 04-24-2024

Managerial Competence and Supervisory Skills of Principals in Catholic Secondary Schools in Eastern Visayas

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Abstract

This study determined the principals' level of managerial competence and supervisory skills as perceived by 12 junior and 2 senior high school principals, 362 teachers and 65 non-teaching personnel in 12 Catholic schools in Eastern Visayas. The study employed mixed-method research design. A descriptive device - survey questionnaires in 2 parts were used to determine the level of managerial competence and supervisory skills of principals. The correlational design was to determine the relationship between the managerial competence and the supervisory skills of the principals. Analysis of Variance and Pearson Product Moment Correlation were used in the study. The study revealed that principals were very highly competent in their managerial functions and very highly skilled in their supervisory tasks. It further revealed that there was significant relationship between their levels of managerial competence and supervisory skills. For the qualitative data, the managerial challenges of the principals were on the small number of enrolments, high turnover of teachers, and the new normal challenge of COVID 19. On supervision, challenges include conflict among people of diverse personalities and insubordination and non-compliance of some teachers.

Keywords: *managerial competence, supervisory skills, principals, catholic secondary schools*

Introduction

Like all educational establishments, private schools in the Philippines have their own characteristics, whether they are nonsectarian or connected to a particular religion. Additionally, private schools are established in accordance with state law, managed fairly, and guided by the appropriate authorities' orders. (Article 14, Section 4, Philippine Constitution of 1987). The secondary private schools must satisfy all the requirements of the government through the Department of Education (DepEd) to be able to get the government recognition to operate in accordance of the standards set forth by DepEd (2011 Manual of Regulations for Private School in Basic Education Article IV, Section 32). And to carry out the DepEd standards, the principal of the high school education must have a master's degree with gained knowledge in the secondary school instruction with competent managerial expertise (2011 Manual of Regulation for Private Schools in Basic Education Article IV, Section 56).

One of the shared responsibilities of the school principals is to do well with their administrative function of leading /directing and to ensure that all teachers, counselors, and the rest of the support staff are working together in the direction of the shared aspirations and at the same time enhancing excellence and advantageous chances. With good and strong administrator, the school can achieve the quality of excellence mandated by the people in education sector and the board of trustees and produce professionals who are cultured and well informed and equipped for facing complex positions, (Olorunsola & Belo, 2018).

Onyeike and Nwosu (2018) state that the administrator as the leader of the secondary institution must play some important roles in moving the school forward and in assuring the achievement qualitative learning which is the goal of very school. One of such goal is supervision of instruction. (Adeyeni, cited in Onyeike & Nwosu (2018) explains that supervision is the process of administration which involves the push to manage everyday activities of the individual or group of people working in the school system with the principal as the leader.

The formal power and structure of the private Catholic school must be clearly and briefly stated in the constitution and by- laws of the school. This is imperative hence conflict is unavoidable in a learning institution with diverse kind of stakeholders particularly the students. Conflict management must have set of guidelines to follow. Members of the Board should keep a copy of the school's constitution and by-laws and parents too should be given copies for proper guidance.

In the private Catholic secondary schools, which among its mission is offering quality Christian education, the school Board of Trustees must look for a school head or principal who is laden with sufficient managerial competence and supervisory skills. He/she must be able to translate the strategic plan generated by the school Board in the daily operation of the school. Thus, the commitment of the private Catholic secondary school in the Philippines in providing quality Christian education to the learners will be realized.

One of the major problems of most private schools especially the small ones is on the financial aspect. The main reason of the fast turnover of teachers after two to three years is the meager salary from private secondary schools. Tuition fee increase is a weak solution to the problem due to the existence of government institutions in the cities, municipalities and barangays to carry out the Education for All (EFA) program of the government through the Department of Education. Managing and supervising low salaried staff is a challenge to school administrators (Sachi, 2022).

Knowing the management competence and supervisory ability of the head of the learning institution will give a more acceptable learning environment for the students and a working place for the employees and teachers.

In this study, the researcher aims to contribute to Psychology and Education by determining the managerial and supervisory competence of secondary catholic school principals which in turn give recommendations on how to improve their practice in managing the education institution in order to provide a better learning environment for learners and better working conditions for both teachers and school staff.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the managerial competence and supervisory skills of principals of catholic secondary schools in Eastern Visayas. Particularly, the investigation sought to respond to the subsequent queries:

1. What is the level of managerial competence of the school principals as assessed by the principals themselves, the teachers and support staff in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. planning;
 - 1.2. organizing;
 - 1.3. leading; and
 - 1.4. controlling?
2. Are there differences present in the judgement of the three sets of participants on the level the managerial competence of school principals?
3. What is the level of supervisory skills of the principals as assessed by assessed by the principals themselves, teachers and support staff in terms of the following:
 - 3.1. curriculum and instructional supervision;
 - 3.2. organization and personnel management;
 - 3.3. assessing and reporting teaching and learning outcomes;
 - 3.4. school plant, resources and facilities management;
 - 3.5. personal, social growth and professional development; and
 - 3.6. school community linkages and public relations?
4. Is there disparity in the assessment of the three sets of participants as to the level of supervisory skills of the principals?
5. Is there a correlation with levels of managerial competence and supervisory skills of the principals?
6. What glitches confronted the principals along with their managerial and supervisory functions?
7. What preventive measure can be recommended using the outcomes of the investigation?

Literature Review

Managerial Competence of Principals

To have better grasp on what are the works of the secondary school principal, it is worthwhile to be aware of their specific functions. According to Sison and Zorilla (2013), the manager or administrator have four fundamental functions in an organization namely; planning which applies to the task on finding out a propose in the style of acting guided by a thorough knowledge of issues connected and is leading to a certain intention; organizing which is the agreement and connections of tasks and positions which are essentials to accomplish; leading/directing which is focused on the guidance of all efforts toward stated objectives; and controlling which involved with seeing to it that activities are in accordance to what designed by the administration.

According to Campus, (2019) planning is a very significant administrative element in any organization. It is an important part of instructional management method that an administrator should have especially in decision – making and implementation. The school administrator needs to always plan for the activities and programs of the school ahead of time. Effective planning get rids of shortages and improper of the school resources.

Ackoff, (cited by Campus, 2019) described planning as the device used in obtaining restrictions in the coming years by present actions through learning inclusively the present issues and use proper method of eradicating problems, expecting parallel occurrences, getting ready for possibilities through devising directions, designing action plans, and supplying well-arranged steps for attaining specified objectives. In short, to plan is to get ready for a goal –oriented action. From these definitions one can conclude that planning is an intentional way of getting prepared in advanced of what is to be done in the future – it is an effort to get things ready for the future.

Akpan (2016) defines organizing as involving building up structures for different resources, for the attainment of organizational goals. In addition, organizing as a managerial function deal with determining what is to be done, by whom and the procedure of doing it. It is also concerned with establishing a structural line of authority and indicating clearly the method of doing a particular job. It involves establishing appropriate channel of communication for information flow in the organization. It includes division of tasks or work, departmentalizing and delegation of authority.

Gabriel (as cited by Musingafi et al., 2014) stated that organizing includes obtaining the essentials which are the ways and means of realizing the goals of the institution. It includes categorization of works into tasks and its alternatives, placing together works which are very similar in nature, delegating of obligations and accountabilities to workers and lastly the giving of responsibility and authority to every worker to carry out their responsibilities appropriately. Consequently, organizing includes prioritizing what is preferred with

the resources at hand. Organizing is in place after the school head formulated a feasible plan.

Organizing includes three important components Argyris (cited in Lunenburg (2010) stated that formulating the system of the organization, obtaining and training human resources, and launching shared plans and systems. Jones (cited in Lunenburg (2010) says the principal creates program of actions and process for authority connections reporting lines breaking of organization into departments, and different managerial and subordinates' obligations. If deemed necessary the school head sets up training programs for inexperienced staff in abilities imperative to perform their designated works. The principal develops official system for communication and information, containing kinds of information to be conveyed, guideline of the flow of communication, and reducing blocks to effectual communication. It is in this aspect of formal communication and information networks and the flow of communication within the organization as well as the establishment of training programs for new personnel by the principals that the gap exists between the present studies with that of Lunenburg (2010).

The leading function involves making decisions and embodying them in specific and general orders and instructions which serve as a guide in an organization. In educational management, the school manager has to provide leadership in dealing with the subordinates as individuals and as groups. The leading/directing function requires the school manager to give orders and directives to other people and expect their compliance. Therefore, for the manager to do this successfully, he/she needs to understand the complex processes leadership – the ability to influence one's subordinates to work willingly and cooperatively in carrying out institutional tasks. Providing this leadership means directing which involves supervising and establishing adequate line of communication so that work processes could be carried out efficiently, (Akpan, 2020). Leading comes after plans are devised and tasks are set up, this is to guide the personnel in attaining the objective of the school. Leading informs the head of the school the reason why employee should desire to execute their work. Leading function is called by several terms such as facilitating, collaborating, directing or actuating. Regardless of the term employed leading involves inspiring and winning people (Northhouse cited in Lunenburg, 2010). As Garvin (2002) stated, the leading function involves directing, instructing, preparing, valuing, control, remunerating, and recruiting. Employment first hand skills to the organization, raising of positions and or moving personnel to another job and charges and separating people from the organization.

The controlling task involves determining how well an actual operation conforms to expected result (Akpan, 2020). This means that if the results fail to meet expectations, an attempt must be made to determine the reason for the failure and remedial action taken accordingly. Controlling ensures that everything occurs in conformity with plan, objectives and standard set. It involves evaluation of workers' performance compared to plan. Controlling is a managerial skill that ensures effective acquisition and use of the organizational resources to achieve stated objectives. Controlling/monitoring is when school heads contrasts anticipated outcomes, and impose required curative act. Departing from former strategy should be thought of when devising novel scheme. Controlling/monitoring is an obligation of a school head. It might plainly made up of roaming round the work place to take notice of what is happening, conversing with students, walking through classrooms, conversing with teachers, or it may involve devising effective information system to monitor the performance standards, these tasks must be conducted if the principal is to be fruitful (Blankstein et al. cited in Lunenburg, 2010).

In all schools the principal performs vital and precise functions in the educational undertakings. In the shoulder of every principal rest the achievement or disappointment of the institution. The principal shall act as educational director, managerial planner and instructional leader. As an instructional overseer, he/she shall make sure of the attainment of effective learning is taking place; he/she should see to it that teachers proficient inspired; provision of sufficient instructional aids; the teacher is focused on his/her teaching responsibilities and is well supervised and given a voice in improving the teaching-learning environment (Matias, 2011).

Supervisory Skills of Principals

In the scenario of the diversified duties and supervisory function of the principals, it is fundamental for them to hone their administrative ability with regards to; subject elements and instruction; organization and personnel supervision; appraisal and giving of account on learning results; equipment and machineries of the school, resources and amenities; individual, communal improvement and professional growth, and school and community connections and civic associations.

The study of Onyeike and Nwosu, (2018) emphasized that the principal as the overseer of the secondary educational institute must play some important roles in moving the school forward and in assuring qualitative learning which is the goal of the school. One of such roles is the supervision of instruction. (Adeyeni cited in Onyeike & Nwosu, 2018) explains that supervision is the process of administration which involves the push to manage everyday activities of individual or group of people working in the school system. The principal is the leader and as (Adesina cited in Onyeike & Nwosu, 2018) observes, the leader in any group is considered as having the best ideas, possessing the greatest understanding of situations and providing the best guidance.

In the same line, Bernard and Goodyear (as cited in Onyeike & Nwosu, 2018) imagined that a counseling intervention, which is a way of helping with personal problems, should be assumed by a mature person as a vocation that emanates from a human person of related vocation. The relations are measurable and extended later with a concomitant justification for improving the skilled functioning of the minor component. Checking on the anticipated standard of the specialized service they provide, in addition he/she acts as a protector to the persons who are to come into the same occupation.

Leigha, as cited in Onyeike and Nwosu (2018), explains that the modern-day supervisor is a friend to the teacher, a counselor, an

energizer, an inspector, a colleague, a partner in progress, and a helper. Project Concern International (as cited in Onyeike & Nwosu, 2018) lists the following among other attributes to the supervisor: “thoughtful and quiet, emphatic and able to put self in another’s shoe, unbiased and non-judgmental.

The Wallace Foundation (cited in Napire, 2019): stated that the principal as the main provider of direction brings considerable influences in the school. Effectual school leader reinforces the entire school in upgrading its educational program and focus on the goals of improving the students in many aspects. The school head should have the attribute of being encouraging and approachable to the students and the faculty members as well, and always look at them as component in the pool of experts giving emphasis on excellent teaching process. School heads performs a significant task of building “group of experts” in the persons of the teachers and the support staff who work hand in hand with them in upgrading teaching and learning process thus encourage soaring hopes and inspire incessant upgrading of their teaching career. Principals are skilled guide who consider documents or records as a way to determine drawbacks and also comprehend its kind and what triggers it to happen.

Supervision and instruction are imperative lately for the reason that it is significant in learning as well as for the quest of upgrading the standard of teaching. As declared by Osakwe (cited in Ekpoh & Eze, (2015), supervision is apprehensive in giving technical help and direction to schoolteachers and students aligned to the direction of the attainment of successful instruction of learning in an educational institution. The school head who is the manager gives professional direction to teachers to enhance and upgrade their ability for effective methods of instruction and to improve the acquisition of knowledge on the part of the students. The school head in performing his/her obligations helps teachers to be high performing in the area of designing lesson plans and notes prior to actual teaching. Teachers apply effective methods of teaching with appropriate use of materials for instruction, performing other works such as keeping and upholding school records, management of classroom and others. Through the task overseeing the school head can give valuable advice and guidance to teachers that may result to profound imparting of knowledge that occurs in the classroom. To succeed in the pursuit of an effectual educational administration, the principals should pursue excellence in rendering quality and up - dated services relevant to the desired offering of quality service to every learner through effective teaching and learning methods and practices. It is made possible through skillful and democratic ways of supervising the performance of human resources in the school setting. The administrators themselves seek to innovate and keep the school abreast with relevant and improved educational programs making everyone in the school organization ready to face the challenges of the ever-changing world of education. Modernization must be welcomed with utmost optimism.

In curriculum and supervisory function of the principal it is his/her obligation to arrange and supervise the procedure of teaching in all areas, he should have mastery of at least two of the subjects taught in the school and the current methodology employed in teaching them. Mbipom (cited in Onyeike & Nwosu, 2018) insists that supervision is helpful in enhancing in teacher’s competency when it involves advancement, like the utilization of new approach, reading curriculum or another orthography.in the same vein, Lashway (cited in Onyeike & Nwosu, 2018) expresses those principals today should likewise serve as pioneers for students’ learning. They should know the program content and pedagogical procedure. They should know, collect and analyze data in a way that fuels excellence.

Onyeike and Nwosu (2018) emphasize that principals ensure regular teaching and learning which will make teachers proficient, skillfully improve development through job assignment. Motivate staff by rewarding the top performers and counseling those who do not meet expectations.

Supervision of learning is the main dimension task that must be carried out by school principals and school supervisors to improve teachers’ abilities in learning. Participating in learning supervision activities, both individually and in groups, is part of teacher professional development activities. How it is implemented in schools needs to be studied more deeply (Maisyaroh et al. 2021).

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a mixed-method research design, which involves the descriptive-correlational and phenomenological qualitative research methods. The researcher utilized interviews to gather information from the principals in the qualitative part of the study. A descriptive device was applied in determining the level of the managerial competence of the principals in terms of planning, organizing, leading and controlling and the supervisory skills in terms of: curriculum and instructional supervision, organization and personnel management, planning, assessing and reporting teaching learning outcomes, school plant resources and facilities management, personal social growth and professional development and school, community linkages and public relations that will be based on the assessment of the administrators themselves, the teachers and the support staff.

The correlational design was employed to verify the relationship concerning the principal’s managerial competence and his/her supervisory expertise based on the assessment of the three groups of respondents. Analysis of Variance and Pearson Product Moment Correlation were the statistical tools applied in the study while Thematic Analysis were used to analyze qualitative data from the interview.

Participants

The researcher used total enumeration of principals, and full-time teaching staff and non-teaching personnel of the identified private secondary Catholic Schools in the cities of Eastern Visayas. Among the respondents were 12 junior high school and 2 senior high school principals, a total of 14 principals and 362 teachers and 65 non-teaching personnel who were directly managed and supervised by the principal.

Instruments

The researcher used adopted structured survey questionnaires as the main instrument and conducted short interviews with the principals with specified guide questions that lead to the sharing of the problems and challenges, they experienced as secondary school principals and how they cope with the problems and challenges encountered. The interview was video recorded.

The Survey Questionnaires used for the three groups of respondents, namely; the principals themselves, the teachers and the non-teaching personnel using the same 10 item-indicators on the four managerial competencies of school administrators in Planning, Organizing, Leading and controlling adapted from Erfe (1999) was used. Another adopted questionnaire from Matias (2011) was used to measure the degree of the administrative expertise of school heads in terms of: curriculum and instructional supervision, organization and personnel management, planning, assessing and reporting teaching learning outcomes, school plant resources and facilities management, personal social growth and professional development and school community linkages and public relations.

Part 1 of the questionnaire was on the level of managerial competence of the school principals with 4 sub parts: Planning, Organizing, Leading and Controlling. Each of the sub-parts has 10 item-indicators each. Part II of the questionnaire was on the level of the supervisory skills of the school administrators with 6 sub-parts: Curriculum and Instructional Supervision; Organization and Personnel Management; Planning and assessing and reporting teaching learning outcomes; School plant, resources and facilities management; Personal, social growth and professional development; and School community and public relations. Each of the component has 5 item-indicators each.

The instruments used the 5-point Likert Scale Model for the respondents' responses, with 5 as the highest value and 1 as the lowest. A Semi-Structured Interview Guide Interview Guide were used to elicit answers to the questions on the problems of the school principals in their managerial competence and supervisory skills and how they cope with these problems.

Procedure

The researcher sought permission and approval of the Dissertation Committee and the Dean of the Graduate School to administer the research instrument. The questionnaires were distributed to the identified respondents to obtain the needed the unpredictable facts specified in the problems of the study. The 6-page questionnaires had directions for the respondents to make the corresponding responses. The questionnaires for the school principals, the teachers and non-teaching personnel were entrusted to the principals and were retrieved after five days. In one school in Tacloban City the research instruments were distributed by the researcher to the principal, to the teachers and to the non-teaching personnel and were retrieved right after they finished in less than an hour. The conduct of the research instruments started on January 29, 2020 and was completed on February 27, 2020 in all schools included in the study.

For the challenges experienced by the principals in administering and supervising the school, the following guide questions were formulated: (1) how do you find the task of managing and supervising the school? (2) Were there issues and challenges in your managing and supervising tasks? (3) How did you manage those problems encountered? (4) If problems in managerial competence and supervisory skills surface, how would you cope with these, this time? And any effective way of coping managerial competence and supervisory issues you can recommend to your fellow secondary administrators, especially for the new ones? The interview was conducted a one-on-one and was video recorded.

Ethical Considerations

The highest ethical standards were applied in this research. The researcher wrote formal letters to school heads requesting permission to administer the survey questionnaires to their respective schools' principals, faculty and non-teaching staff. The researcher's actual administration of the research instruments was done only after the needed approval of the school heads were secured. The respondents were assured that the individual data gathered from the respondents would be taken for aggregate data treated with high confidentiality. The participants of this study were notified of the purpose as well as the aim of the investigation Anonymity of the respondents was strictly observed.

Results and Discussion

The section puts forward findings of investigation on management competence and supervisory skill of the administrators in textual form with the corresponding tables. It also presents the implications derived from the results.

Level of Managerial Competence School Principals in Planning, Organizing, Leading, and Controlling as Assessed by the Administrators Themselves, the Teachers and the Support Staff

This section determined the level of managerial competence of the private secondary principals in Eastern Visayas in terms of planning, organizing, leading and controlling as assessed by the principals themselves, the teachers and the non-teaching personnel. The findings introduced in the following tables.

Level of Managerial Competence of the Principals in Planning

One of the sub-variables in the management competence of the school principal is planning. The results of the data gathered are presented in Table1.

School principals. Along planning, the principals gave themselves the highest rating of 4.36 in two indicators number 6 and 9. Indicator number 6 tells that they are very highly competent in clearly setting specific goals and objectives which can easily be translated into action by the school staff, and in indicator number 9 states that they are very highly competent in informing concerned people on time when plans are changed. And in item number 10 is 4.07 which is interpreted as highly competent in coordinating the formulation of criteria for evaluating institutional plan. The principals registered an overall mean of 4.21 interpreted as very highly competent in their managerial function of planning. A lowest rating of 4.07 in item number 8 which is interpreted as highly competent in periodically examining the strength and weaknesses of the school's staff in delivering specified tasks through observations, structure and unstructured interviews and formal evaluation using standardized evaluation tools and made known the result to them through individual conferences. And in item number 10 which is interpreted as highly competent in coordinating the formulation of criteria for evaluating institutional plan. The principals registered an overall mean of 4.21 interpreted as very highly competent in their managerial function of planning

Teachers. The teachers' highest rating of 4.53 is in item number 4, interpreted as very highly competent in explaining policies to guide the school staff on what to improve of the institutional operations. Their lowest rating is 4.20 in item number 10 and interpreted as highly competent in coordinating the formulation of criteria for evaluating institutional plan. The overall mean of 4.39 interpreted as very highly competent. This suggests that teachers look at their principals as very highly competent in planning

Support Staff. The highest rating from the support staff is 4.69 from indicator numbers 4 and 6. Indicator number 4 states that the principals are very highly competent in explaining policies to guide the school staff on what to improve of the institutional operations. Item number 6 says that the principals are very highly competent in clearly setting specific goals and objectives which can easily be translated into action by the school staff. They gave them the lowest rating of 4.40 in item number 3 which still interpreted as very highly competent in budgeting or allocating available resources to accomplish the objectives of the institution. An overall mean from the support staff is 4.55 is an implication that they consider the principals to be very highly competent when it comes to planning.

Table 1. *Level of Managerial Competence of School Principals in Planning as Assessed by Principals Themselves, the Teachers and the Support Staff*

Indicators	Principals		Teachers		Support Staff		Overall Mean	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Our Principals...								
1.predetermine the future courses of action to be taken to improve the institution by making forecasts on a systematic and continuing basis	4.14	HC	4.42	VHC	4.58	VHC	4.38	VHC
2.pinpoint the specific result to be achieved by setting goals and objectives to guide the operations of the institution	4.21	VHC	4.47	VHC	4.64	VHC	4.44	VHC
3.budget or allocate available resources to achieve the goals of the school	4.07	HC	4.36	VHC	4.40	VHC	4.27	VHC
4.explain policies to guide the school staff on what to improve of the operations	4.29	VHC	4.53	VHC	4.69	VHC	4.50	VHC
5.allow the school staff's participation in planning and policy making	4.29	VHC	4.35	VHC	4.55	VHC	4.39	VHC
6.clearly set a specific goals and objectives which can easily be translated into action by the school staff.	4.36	VHC	4.43	VHC	4.69	VHC	4.49	VHC
7.give importance to alternative steps suggested by subordinates.	4.29	VHC	4.33	VHC	4.49	VHC	4.37	VHC
8.periodically examine the strength and weaknesses of the school's staff in delivering specified tasks through observations, structure and unstructured interviews and formal evaluation using standardized evaluation tools and made	4.07	HC	4.37	VHC	4.44	VHC	4.29	VHC

known the result to them through individual conferences								
9.inform concerned people on time when plans are changed, and	4.36	VHC	4.34	VHC	4.47	VHC	4.39	VHC
10.coordinate the formulation of criteria for evaluating institutional plans	4.07	HC	4.20	HC	4.51	VHC	4.26	VHC
Overall Mean	4.21	VHC	4.39	VHC	4.55	VHC	4.38	VHC

Legend: HVC-Very Highly Competent; HC-Highly Competent

Level of Managerial Competence of School Principals in Organizing

Table 2 presents the assessments results from the three groups of respondents namely the school principals themselves, the teachers and the non-teaching personnel on the organizing competence of the school principals.

School principals. Taken from assessment of the principals, the highest rating they conferred to themselves is 4.50 for indicators number 3 and 8. This signifies that in indicator number 3, they are very highly competent in delegating or entrusting responsibility and authority to others, and in indicator number 8, it indicates that they are very highly competent in forming groups or teams to perform vital tasks in the institution. The lowest rating of 4.07 is registered for both numbers 4 and 10. This suggests that school principals are highly competent in seeing to it that the unity of command permeate throughout the organization; that is a subordinate report only to one head, and in indicator number 10 they are highly competent in forming groups or teams to assess the accomplishment of the school staff. The general average of 4.29 was registered for the principals described as very highly competent in organizing.

Teachers. As indicated by the teachers, the highest rating of 4.50 the teachers gave to the principals is on indicator number 3 interpreted as the principals are very highly competent in delegating or entrusting responsibility and authority to others. The lowest rating was 4.33 on indicator number 4 still interpreted as very highly competent in seeing to it that unity of command permeates throughout the organization, that is a subordinate report only to one head. An overall mean of 4.41 suggests that their principals are very highly competent in organizing

Support Staff. As shown in the table, the support rated their principals 4.62 in indicator number 2-the highest and is interpreted as they are very highly competent in grouping the work to form a well-balanced organizational unit. The lowest is 4.40 in indicator number 5 still interpreted as very highly competent in logically dividing the major tasks into sub tasks for easy and accurate completion. An overall mean of 4.50 was registered to describe the principals as very highly competent.

Table 2. *Level of Managerial Competence of School Principals in Organizing as Assessed by the Principals Themselves, the Teachers and the Support Staff*

Indicators	Principals		Teachers		Support Staff		Overall Mean	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
<i>Our Principals...</i>								
1.explain the organizational structure to identify lines of authority in the institution	4.14	HC	4.46	VHC	4.56	VHC	4.38	VHC
2. group the work to form a well-balanced organizational unit.	4.36	VHC	4.46	VHC	4.62	VHC	4.48	VHC
3.delegate or entrust responsibility and authority to others	4.50	VHC	4.50	VHC	4.51	VHC	4.50	VHC
4.see to it that the unity of command permeates throughout the organization; a subordinate report to only one head	4.07	HC	4.33	VHC	4.44	VHC	4.28	VHC
5.logically divide major tasks into sub tasks for easy and accurate completion	4.29	VHC	4.46	VHC	4.40	VHC	4.38	VHC
6.allocate available resources and is consistent with the plan	4.21	VHC	4.35	VHC	4.44	VHC	4.41	VHC
7. evaluate organizational strategies of the institution	4.21	VHC	4.45	VHC	4.58	VHC	4.41	VHC
8.form groups or teams to perform vital tasks in the institution	4.50	VHC	4.37	VHC	4.47	VHC	4.44	VHC
9.coordinate performances of duties and responsibilities of school staff, and	4.36	VHC	4.45	VHC	4.53	VHC	4.44	VHC
10.form groups or teams to evaluate the performance of the school staff	4.07	HC	4.34	VHC	4.44	VHC	4.28	VHC
Overall Mean	4.29	VHC	4.41	VHC	4.50	VHC	4.40	VHC

Legend: HVC-Very Highly Competent; HC-Highly Competent

Level of Managerial Competence of School Principals in Leading

Scores in Table 3 reveal the level on the managerial competence of the principals in leading. Leading in this study is considered as dealing with the teaching and non-teaching staff successfully. It suggests on developing and inspiring the staff to become efficient and effective workers in the academe. It is in this managerial competence that a leader invests more time with the people they are working

with, giving those witnesses for a purpose of influencing them to give the best of their services to the organization.

School Principals. The school principals' highest self-rating of 4.43 are in indicators number 2, 5, 9, and 10. These mean that, indicator number 2 they are very highly competent in motivating, inspiring, encouraging, and impelling others to take action willingly and enthusiastically, indicator number 5, they are very highly competent in coordinating all individual and group efforts within the organization, number 9 implies that principals are very highly competent in allowing teamwork and integration of functions, and indicator number 10 the principals are very highly competent in coordinating the work of various units and departments in the institution. The lowest rating, they gave to themselves is 4.07 in indicator number 7 which signifies that they are highly competent in offering fair and suitable rewards for services rendered through award and recognition. An overall mean of 4.35 suggests that the principals consider themselves very highly competent in leading.

Teachers. A highest rating of 4.50 from the teachers in indicator number 9 describes the school principals as very highly competent in allowing teamwork and integration of functions. The lowest rating of 4.33 in indicator number 4 indicates that the principals are still very highly competent in seeing to it that the subordinates know where they stand by keeping them informed. And an overall mean of 4.41 describes the principals as very highly competent in leading.

The support staff. The support staff highest rating of 4.73 in indicator number 9 tells that the principals are very highly competent in allowing teamwork and integration of functions in the institution. The lowest rating of 4.41 in indicator number 4, relates that they are very highly competent in seeing to it that the subordinates know where they stand by keeping them informed. An overall mean of 4.56 discloses the principals to be very highly competent in leading.

Table 3. Level of Managerial Competence of School Principals in Leading as Assessed by the Principals Themselves, the Teachers and Support Staff

Indicators Our Principals...	Principals		Teachers		Support Staff		Overall Mean	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1.secure understanding between myself and others through dialogues and conferences	4.36	VHC	4.46	VHC	4.60	VHC	4.47	VHC
2.motivate, inspire, encourage, and impel others to take action willingly and enthusiastically	4.43	VHC	4.46	VHC	4.70	VHC	4.53	VHC
3.give subordinate the credit when due	4.29	VHC	4.50	VHC	4.49	VHC	4.42	VHC
4.see to it that the subordinates know where they stand by keeping them informed	4.36	VHC	4.33	VHC	4.41	VHC	4.36	VHC
5.coordinate all individual and group efforts within the organization	4.43	VHC	4.46	VHC	4.46	VHC	4.45	VHC
6.encourage the subordinates to take their own initiative in the performance of their tasks	4.36	VHC	4.35	VHC	4.59	VHC	4.43	VHC
7. offer fair and suitable rewards for services rendered through award and recognition	4.07	HC	4.45	VHC	4.44	VHC	4.32	VHC
8.adopt open-line communication policy	4.36	VHC	4.37	VHC	4.54	VHC	4.42	VHC
9.allow teamwork and integration of functions, and	4.43	VHC	4.45	VHC	4.73	VHC	4.53	VHC
10.coordinate the work of various units and departments in the institution	4.43	VHC	4.34	VHC	4.66	VHC	4.47	VHC
Overall Mean	4.35	VHC	4.41	VHC	4.56	VHC	4.44	VHC

Legend: HVC-Very Highly Competent; HC-Highly Competent

Managerial Competence' level of Principals in Controlling

Table 4. Level of Management Competence of School Principals in Controlling as Assessed by Principals Themselves, the Teachers and Support Staff

Indicators Our Principals...	Principals		Teachers		Support Staff		Overall Mean	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1.develop performance standards to assess the work of the people by formulating objective and clear criteria	4.21	VHC	4.45	VHC	4.62	VHC	4.42	VHC
2.observe classes/performance of the teaching and support staff in order to determine the teacher's teaching proficiency/support staff work efficiency	4.29	VHC	4.47	VHC	4.57	VHC	4.44	VHC
3.evaluate the performance of the school	4.36	VHC	4.43	VHC	4.62	VHC	4.47	VHC

staff by means of determining the extent to which they attained institutional goals								
4.enable people to gain control over their work space, sharing the exercise of power	4.14	HC	4.32	VHC	4.44	VHC	4.30	VHC
5.arrange for training and development opportunities so performances improved	4.57	VHC	4.35	VHC	4.35	VHC	4.42	VHC
6.exercise consistency in disciplinary measures and policies	4.43	VHC	4.36	VHC	4.40	VHC	4.39	VHC
7. observe consistently sanctions against faults and errors.	4.29	VHC	4.31	VHC	4.22	VHC	4.27	VHC
8.communicate performance results to the staff being rated through dialogue and individual conferences	4.36	VHC	4.35	VHC	4.38	VHC	4.36	VHC
9.undertake corrective measures and actions that solve conflicts	4.29	VHC	4.40	VHC	4.40	VHC	4.39	VHC
10.conduct dialogue to resolve differences of opinion among the school staff members	4.36	VHC	4.38	VHC	4.42	VHC	4.38	VHC
Overall Mean	4.33	VHC	4.38	VHC	4.44	VHC	4.38	VHC

Legend: HVC-Very Highly Competent; HC-Highly Competent

Summary of the standard of managerial competence of principals in private Secondary Catholic School in the cities in Eastern Visayas

Table 5 shows the summary on the level of managerial competence of school principals in private secondary Catholic schools in the cities of Eastern Visayas exhibiting the overall means of each of the four managerial competencies assessed by school heads themselves, the teachers and the support staff. It is evident, based on the summary of the overall mean from three groups of respondents is that the school principals are very highly competent in their managerial competencies of planning, organizing, leading, and controlling.

Table 5. Summary Table on the Level of Managerial Competence of Principals in Secondary Private Catholic Schools in Eastern Visayas

Principals	Principals' self-Assessment		Teachers		Non-Teaching Personnel	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Principal A	4.90	VHC	4.74	VHC	4.65	VHC
Principal B	3.90	HC	4.64	VHC	4.35	VHC
Principal C	3.90	HC	4.64	VHC	4.55	VHC
Principal D	3.75	HC	4.15	HC	4.50	VHC
Principal E	4.63	VHC	4.71	VHC	4.69	VHC
Principal F	4.28	VHC	4.56	VHC	4.40	VHC
Principal G	4.00	HC	4.42	VHC	3.98	HC
Principal H	4.80	VHC	4.58	VHC	4.59	VHC
Principal I	4.35	VHC	4.43	VHC	4.71	VHC
Principal J	4.75	VHC	4.41	VHC	4.90	VHC
Principal K	4.93	VHC	4.73	VHC	5.00	VHC
Principal L	4.00	HC	3.80	HC	4.75	VHC
Principal M	4.23	VHC	4.62	VHC	4.60	VHC
Principal N	3.73	HC	4.34	VHC	3.53	HC

Legend: VHC- Very Highly Competent; HC –Highly Competent; MC – Moderately Competent

School Principal. It can be noted that among the 14 principals, principal K registered the highest self-rating of 4.93 interpreted as very highly competent, while principal N has the lowest self-rating mean of 3.73 interpreted as highly competent. It can be gleaned from table 5 that of 14 principals eight assessed themselves as very highly competent in their managerial functions of planning, organizing, leading and controlling, and six rated themselves as highly competent.

Teachers. Principal A obtained the highest rating of 4.74 from the teachers' assessment interpreted as very highly competent. Principal L has the lowest rating of 3.80 from the teachers interpreted as highly competent. Of the 14 principals 12 obtained ratings with very highly competent interpretation and two are rated 4.15 and 3.80 which are interpreted as highly competent.

Support Staff. The highest rating from the support staff is 5, interpreted as very highly competent for principal K, while the ratings of 3.98 and 3.53 are given to principals G and N respectively interpreted as highly competent. There are 12 out of 14 principals whose assessments from the support staff imply that they are very highly competent in their administrative functions of planning, organizing, leading and controlling.

Comparison on the Level of Managerial Competence of the school principals based on the evaluation of principals themselves, teachers as well as the support staff on areas of planning, organizing, leading and controlling

The test of difference on the dissimilarities on the assessment among the three groups of participants which includes the principals themselves, the teachers and the support staff on their level of managerial competence that includes planning, organizing, leading and controlling, the analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used. The result is portrayed in Table 6.

Table 6. *Test of difference on the Level of Managerial Competence of the School Principals Assessed by the Principals’ Themselves, the Teachers and the Support Staff*

Management Competency	F-value	p-level	Interpretation
Planning	1.098	0.344	Not Significant
Organizing	0.452	0.640	Not Significant
Leading	0.205	0.818	Not Significant
Controlling	0.554	0.574	Not significant

Significance is set at 0.05 probability level

As gleaned from Table 6 it can be noted that the computed F-value on planning is not significant at 1.098. Practically and in like manner, organizing, leading and controlling yielded F-value 0.452, 0.205, and 0.554 respectively. The p-level is less than the level of significance at 0.05 level.

The findings indicate that the assessment of the principals themselves do not differ essentially in the agreement of the managerial competence of planning, organizing, leading and controlling. Moreover, the results can be deduced that the self- evaluation of the principals were confirmed by both the teachers and the non-teaching personnel as the assessed their principals with high mean ratings along the different indicators. Thus, the hypothesis that there are no significant differences on the assessments of three sets of participants on the level management competence of the school principals on areas of planning, organizing, leading and controlling is not rejected.

Level of Supervisory Skill of the school principals as assessed by the principals themselves, the teachers and the support staff

The level of supervisory skills of the secondary school principals in 6 areas namely; (1) curriculum and instructional supervision, (2) organization and personnel management, (3) planning, assessing and reporting teaching learning outcomes, (4) school plant, resources and facilities management, (5) personal, social growth and professional development, and (6) school community and public relations are presented in the following tables. Curriculum and instructional supervision is a supervisory skill that is intended for the improvement of teaching and learning. It includes but not limited to classroom observations that could serve as basis for evaluation of teachers with the purpose of helping them in improving classroom performances. The results are presented in Table 7.

As shown in Table 7 the principals’ level of supervisory skill on curriculum and instructional supervision reveals that generally the principals are very highly skilled in supervising the curriculum and instruction of the school as indicated in the overall mean of 4.27, 4.37 and 4.60 from the principals themselves, the teachers and non-teaching personnel respectively. All ratings were interpreted as very highly skilled.

School principals. The school principals’ highest rating of 4.50 interpreted as very highly skilled is on indicator 1 that is coordinating with other schools’ principals in the Implementation of DepEd Orders, and in the implementation of institutional programs and projects. The lowest ratings of 4.14 are given to items 2, 3 and 4 which are interpreted as highly competent. Item 2 is about guiding teachers convey precise and upgraded lesson content applying suitable procedures, styles, plans, approaches and strategies. Item 3 is on helping teachers choose, get ready, and apply on hands instructional tools and other teaching materials apt to the students and teaching goals, and item 4 is concerned on helping the teachers adjust the lesson goals, procedures, learning activities, and teaching aids suitable for the students and teaching aims about helping the teachers adjust the lesson goals, procedures, learning activities, and teaching aids suitable for the students and teaching aims. These are all interpreted as highly skilled. A general average 4.33 suggests that principals are very highly skilled on curriculum as well as instructional supervision.

Table 7. *Supervisory Skills Level of School Principals in Curriculum and Instructional Supervision as Assessed by Principals Themselves, the Teachers and Support Staff*

Indicators Our Principals...	Principals		Teachers		Support Staff		Overall Mean	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1.Coordinate with other schools’ administrators in implementation of DepEd Orders, and in the implementation of institutional programs and projects	4.50	VHS	4.53	VHS	4.64	VHS	4.55	VHS
2.guide teachers deliver accurate and updated knowledge using appropriate methodologies, approaches, and strategies	4.14	HS	4.36	VHS	4.55	VHS	4.35	VHS
3.help teachers select, prepare and utilize available technology and other instructional materials	4.14	HS	4.33	VHS	4.57	VHS	4.34	VHS

appropriate to the learners and the learning objectives									
4.assist teachers align the lesson objectives, teaching methods, learning activities and instructional materials or resources appropriate to the learners	4.14	HS	4.26	VHS	4.60	VHS	4.33	VHS	
5.hold post teaching conference to evaluate the efficiency of teachers and provide proper mentoring every after class observation	4.14	VHS	4.35	VHS	4.62	VHS	4.43	VHS	
Overall Mean	4.34	VHS	4.38	VHS	4.60	VHS	4.43	VHS	

Legend: HVCS-Very Highly Skilled; HC-Highly Competent skilled

Teachers. Teachers’ highest rating for their principals of 4.53 is on item number 1 which means they are very highly skilled in coordinating with other school administrators in the implementation of DepEd orders, and in the implementation of institutional implementation of institutional programs and project. While the lowest rating of 4.26 in item 4 still interpreted very highly skilled in helping teachers to align the teaching goals, procedures of instruction, activities for learning as well as teaching aids and resources fitted for students’ needs. The general average of 4.38 manifested that the teachers’ assessed the school heads as very highly skilled in curriculum and educational management.

Support Staff. The highest rating from the support staff is 4.64 on number 1 which means that the principals are very highly skilled in coordinating with other school principals in the implementation of DepEd orders, and in the implementation of institutional implementation of institutional programs and project. And the lowest rating of 4.55 still interpreted as very highly skilled is on number 2 which means that the principals are very highly skilled in guiding teachers provide precise and upgraded learning content and applying suitable processes, methods and plans. The overall mean of 4.60 from the non-teaching personnel implies that principals are extremely effective in curriculum and educational management.

Table 8. *Level of Supervisory Skills of Principals in Organization and Personnel Management as Assessed by Principals Themselves, the Teachers and Support Staff*

Indicators <i>Our Principals...</i>	Principals		Teachers		Support Staff		Overall Mean	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1.Coordinate with other schools’ administrators in implementation of DepEd Orders, and in the implementation of institutional programs and projects	4.07	HS	4.40	VHS	4.46	VHS	4.31	VHS
2.guide teachers deliver accurate and updated knowledge using appropriate methodologies, approaches, and strategies	4.14	HS	4.27	VHS	4.48	VHS	4.29	VHS
3.help teachers select, prepare and utilize available technology and other instructional materials appropriate to the learners and the learning objectives	4.43	VHS	4.43	VHS	4.60	VHS	4.48	VHS
4.assist teachers align the lesson objectives, teaching methods, learning activities and instructional materials or resources appropriate to the learners	4.43	VHS	4.41	VHS	4.57	VHS	4.47	VHS
5.hold post teaching conference to evaluate the efficiency of teachers and provide proper mentoring every after-class observation	4.29	VHS	4.38	VHS	4.51	VHS	4.39	VHS
Overall Mean	4.27	VHS	4.38	VHS	4.52	VHS	4.39	VHS

Legend: HVCS-Very Highly Skilled; HC-Highly Competent skilled

School Principals. The school principals’ highest rating of 4.43 interpreted as very highly skilled are in items 3 and 4. These mean that the principals are very highly skilled in the areas of developing and establishing training programs for faculty as well as provision of an ongoing efficient professional enhancement, influencing teachers and support staff to demonstrate individual merits which uphold self-respect for their professions. They rated themselves 4.07 which is lowest on item number 1-interpreted as highly skilled in displaying all the time a consistent high level of performance skills, abilities, upholds initiatives and productivity. An overall mean is registered at 4.27 which denotes they considered themselves very highly skilled in organization and personnel management.

Teachers. The teachers’ highest rating is 4.43 in indicator number 3, interpreted as very highly skilled in developing and organizing in-service training programs for teachers and support staff and in providing continuous and effective professional development. It should be noted that the principals too rated themselves highest in this item which strengthens the validity of the findings. A general average of 4.38 disclosed that teachers looked at the principals as very highly skilled. The lowest rating of 4.27 on item number 2 still interpreted as very highly skilled in giving recognition to deserving teachers and support staff and in recommending scholarships and promotions is more or less aligned with the rating of 4.14 from the principals which even if not the lowest is tantamount only to highly

skilled level. A general average of 4.38 exposed that teacher looked at the principals as very highly skilled in terms of organization and personnel management.

Support Staff. On the part of the support staff the highest rating of 4.60 is on item number 3 which means that the principals are very highly skilled in developing and establishing teachers in service training program as well as provision of an ongoing and efficient professional development scheme. While a lowest rating of 4.46 on number 1 which can still be interpreted as very highly skilled in designing and applying different and appropriate evaluation plan to check and assess instruction and learning. An overall average of 4.52 suggests, principals are very highly skilled in organization and personnel management.

Planning, Assessing and Reporting Teaching Learning Outcomes

Another variable of the study is the supervisory ability of the principals in the areas of planning, assessing and reporting teaching learning outcomes. Results are presented in Table 9.

School Principals. The school principals gave themselves the highest rating of 4.50 in indicator 5 which implies that they are very highly skilled in establishing and maintaining consistent standards of teachers’ and learners’ behavior. And their lowest is 4.07 in item 4 reveals that they are highly skilled in developing and utilizing creative and appropriate instructional planning. An overall mean registered at 4.23 indicated that the principals are very highly skilled in planning, assessing and reporting learning outcomes.

Teachers. The teacher rated the school principals 4.42, the highest in number 3, and a rating of 4.31 in items 2 and 4, the lowest. All ratings from the teachers in all five indicators are interpreted as very highly skilled.

Support Staff. A highest rating of 4.49 on indicator 3 from the support staff indicates that the principals are very highly skilled in keeping precise records, grades, and performance level of learners and teachers while the lowest rating of 4.30 in number 5 showed that the principals are very highly skilled in establishing and maintaining consistent standards of teachers’ and learners’ behavior. The 4.42 overall mean qualifies the principals to the very highly skilled level of planning, assessing and reporting teaching learning outcomes.

Table 9. *Level of Supervisory Skills of School Principals in Terms of Planning, Assessing and Reporting Teaching Learning Outcomes as Assessed by Principals Themselves, the Teachers and Support Staff*

Indicators Our Principals...	Principals		Teachers		Support Staff		Overall Mean	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1.develop and use a variety of appropriate assessment strategies to monitor and evaluate teaching and learning	4.14	HS	4.34	VHS	4.48	VHS	4.32	VHS
2.provide timely and accurate feedback to teachers to encourage them to reflect on and monitor their own teaching/professional growth	4.14	HS	4.31	VHS	4.41	VHS	4.28	VHS
3.keep accurate records, grades and performance level of learners and teachers	4.29	HS	4.42	VHS	4.49	VHS	4.40	VHS
4.develop and utilize creative and appropriate instructional planning	4.07	VHS	4.31	VHS	4.40	VHS	4.26	VHS
5.establish and maintain consistent standards of teachers and learners behavior	4.50	HS	4.38	VHS	4.30	VHS	4.39	VHS
Overall Mean	4.23	VHS	4.37	VHS	4.42	VHS	4.34	VHS

Legend: HVCS-Very Highly Skilled; HC-Highly Competent skilled

School plant, resources and facilities management

Presented in Table 10 are the findings on the level of supervisory skills of the school principals in school plant, resources and facilities management.

Table 10. *Level of Supervisory Skills of School Principals in School Plant, Resources and Facilities Management as Assessed by Principals Themselves, the Teachers and Support Staff*

Indicators Our Principals...	Principals		Teachers		Support Staff		Overall Mean	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. tap government official, non-government agencies for provision of school facilities and equipment.	3.71	HS	4.29	VHS	4.17	HS	4.05	HS
2.assist teachers/support staff with maximum utilization of the school surroundings and equipment without destroying them	4.29	VHS	4.35	VHS	4.40	VHS	4.34	VHS
3.conduct fund-raising campaigns to improve and upgrade the school’s service centers	3.93	HS	4.18	HS	3.95	HS	4.02	HS
4.maintain an accepting, permissive and non-threatening school atmosphere	4.43	VHS	4.43	VHS	4.47	VHS	4.44	VHS

5.observe transparency in money matters, school policy, activities and projects	4.50	VHS	4.42	VHS	4.42	VHS	4.44	VHS
Overall Mean	4.17	HS	4.33	VHS	4.28	VHS	4.26	VHS

Legend: HVCS-Very Highly Skilled; HC-Highly Competent skilled

Principals. The highest rating from the school principals themselves is 4.50 in item number 5 indicates that they considered themselves very highly skilled in observing transparency in money matters, school policy, activities and projects. While the lowest rating is 3.71 in indicator number 1 means they look at themselves as only highly skilled in tapping school government and non-government agencies for the provision of school facilities and equipment. The overall mean of 4.17 indicated that they are highly competent in their supervisory function of school plant resources and facilities management.

Teachers. The teachers gave their highest rating of 4.43 on item 4 implies that the school principals are very highly skilled in maintaining an accepting, permissive and non-threatening school atmosphere. The lowest rating of 4.18 in item number 3 points out that the school principals are only highly skilled in conducting fund-raising campaigns to improve and upgrade the school’s service centers. An overall rating of 4.33 implies that the teachers look at their principals as very highly skilled in school plant resources and facilities management.

Support Staff. From the point of view of the support staff, a highest rating of 4.47 in item number 4 suggests that the school principals are very highly competent in maintaining an accepting, permissive and non-threatening school atmosphere while the lowest rating of 3.95 in indicator number 3 conveys the message that the principals are only highly competent in conducting fund-raising campaign to improve and upgrade the school’s service centers. The overall mean of 4.28 proposes that they assess their principals as very highly skilled in school plant resources and facilities management.

Personal, social growth and professional development

Presented in Table 11 are the results of the assessments of the school principals’ supervisory skill of personal, social growth and professional development.

Table 11. Level of Supervisory Skills of School Principals in Personal, Social Growth and Professional Development as Assessed by Principals Themselves the Teachers and Support Staff

Indicators Our Principals...	Principals		Teachers		Support Staff		Overall Mean	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1.manifest personal qualities like enthusiasm, flexibility, caring attitude, collegiality among others	4.46	VHS	4.47	VHS	4.66	VHS	4.53	VHS
2.improve supervisory performance based on feedback from colleagues, superiors and others	4.38	VHS	4.42	VHS	4.50	VHS	4.43	VHS
3.update oneself with recent development in education through readings, attendance in continuing personal education and or training and seminars	4.46	VHS	4.49	VHS	4.68	VHS	4.54	VHS
4.demonstrate educational philosophy of school supervision	4.31	VHS	4.45	VHS	4.53	VHS	4.43	VHS
5. maintain appropriate appearance and decorum at all times	4.62	VHS	4.53	VHS	4.59	VHS	4.58	VHS
Overall Mean	4.45	HS	4.47	VHS	4.59	VHS	4.50	VHS

Legend: HVCS-Very Highly Skilled; HC-Highly Competent skilled

Principals. The principals’ highest rating is 4.62 in item number 5 interpreted as very highly skilled in maintaining appropriate appearance and decorum at all times, while the lowest is 4.31 on item number 4, still interpreted as very highly competent in demonstrating educational philosophy of school supervision. The overall mean of 4.34 indicates the principals’ self- perception as very highly skilled in areas of personal, social growth and professional development.

Teachers. Teachers’ highest rating of 4.53 is on number 5 which means the school principals are very highly competent in maintaining appropriate appearance and decorum at all times. The lowest rating of 4.42 takes place on indicator number 2, but still with a very highly skilled in interpretation on improving supervisory performance based on feedback from colleagues, superiors and others. A general average of 4.47 shows principals are very highly skilled in the area of personal, social growth and personal development.

Non-Teaching Personnel. The non-teaching personnel gave their highest rating of 4.68 on item number 3 which is interpreted as the school principals are very highly skilled in updating oneself in latest changes in education by means of readings, attendance of ongoing personal development programs, trainings and seminars, The overall mean of 4.59 implies they are highly skilled principals.

School - Community Linkages and Public Relation

Table 12 presents the assessments results of three sets of participants namely; principals themselves, teachers and support staff on the school principals’ supervisory skill on school-community linkages and public relations.

School Principals. The highest rating of 4.54 in indicator number 4 from the school principals themselves indicates that they are very

highly skilled in maintaining an open line communication with parents, teachers and the community. Their lowest rating is 4.38 in Indicator number 2 still implies that they are very highly skilled in involving the community in sharing accountability for learners' achievement. The implication of the overall mean of 4.46 is the principals' perception of themselves as very high skilled in school-community linkages and public relations.

Teachers. From the teachers' point of view, they give their school principals the highest rating of 4.61 in item number 1 indicating that they are very highly skilled in their supervisory function of informing parents, learners, and other stakeholders regarding school policies and processes. The lowest mark of 4.43 falls on indicator number 5 still signifies that the school principals are very highly skilled in coordinating with the community and public officials for the wholesome growth and development of students, and the personnel of the school. An overall mean is registered at 4.51 indicates they are very highly skilled principals in the assessment of the teachers.

Non-teaching personnel. The non-teaching staff give the highest rating of 4.77 on statement number 1. This means that the school principals are very highly skilled informing parents, learners, and other stakeholders regarding school policies and procedures. Their lowest mark of 4.37 fell on item number 5 which is still interpreted as the school principals are very highly skilled in coordinating with the community and public officials for the wholesome growth and development of all the students and the personnel in the school. The 4.57 over all mean speaks out the very highly skilled valuation of the non-teaching personnel on their principals.

Table 12. *Level of Supervisory Skills of Principals in School Community Linkages and Public Relation as Assessed by Principals Themselves, the Teachers and the Support Staff*

Indicators Our Principals...	Principals		Teachers		Support Staff		Overall Mean	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1.infrom parents, learners and other stakeholders regarding school policies and procedures	4.46	VHS	4.61	VHS	4.77	VHS	4.61	VHS
2.involve the community in sharing accountability for learners' achievement	4.38	VHS	4.47	VHS	4.60	VHS	4.48	VHS
3.provide leadership in the formulation and implementation of all educational programs in school and community	4.46	VHS	4.52	VHS	4.55	VHS	4.51	VHS
4.maintain an open line communication with parents, teachers and the community	4.54	VHS	4.53	VHS	4.55	VHS	4.54	VHS
5.coordinate with the community and public officials for the wholesome growth and development of all students and other personnel in the school	4.46	VHS	4.43	VHS	4.37	VHS	4.42	VHS
Overall Mean	4.46	VHS	4.51	VHS	4.57	VHS	4.51	VHS

Legend: HVCS-Very Highly Skilled; HC-Highly Competent skilled

Summary of the Findings on the Degree of Supervisory Skills of School Principals

Table 13 exhibits the summary on the level of supervisory skills of the principals in private secondary schools in Eastern Visayas as assessed by principals themselves, teachers and support staff.

Table 13. *Summary Table on the Level of the Supervisory Skills of the School Principals in the Catholic Secondary Schools in Eastern Visayas*

Indicators Our Principals...	Principals		Teachers		Support Staff		Overall Mean	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1.infrom parents, learners and other stakeholders regarding school policies and procedures	4.46	VHS	4.61	VHS	4.77	VHS	4.61	VHS
2.involve the community in sharing accountability for learners' achievement	4.38	VHS	4.47	VHS	4.60	VHS	4.48	VHS
3.provide leadership in the formulation and implementation of all educational programs in school and community	4.46	VHS	4.52	VHS	4.55	VHS	4.51	VHS
4.maintain an open line communication with parents, teachers and the community	4.54	VHS	4.53	VHS	4.55	VHS	4.54	VHS
5.coordinate with the community and public officials for the wholesome growth and development of all students and other personnel in the school	4.46	VHS	4.43	VHS	4.37	VHS	4.42	VHS
Overall Mean	4.46	VHS	4.51	VHS	4.57	VHS	4.51	VHS

Legend: HVCS-Very Highly Skilled; HC-Highly Competent skilled

Principals. It could be noted that on the principals' self-rating, principal K's self-rating is the highest at 4.97 interpreted as very highly skilled in his/her institutional supervisory task. On the other hand, principal N's rating registered as the lowest at 3.33 interpreted as moderately skilled. Of the 14 principals eight (8) are on the level of very highly skilled, five (5) highly skilled and one (1) moderately skilled.

Teachers. The highest rating from the teachers is 4.75 for principal K, while the lowest is 3.41 interpreted as highly skilled for teacher B. Of the 14 principals, 13 are at the very highly skilled level in terms of supervisory skills.

Non-Teaching Personnel. The non-teaching personnel’s highest mean of 5.00 interpreted as very highly skilled is on principal K, while the lowest which is 3.47 interpreted as highly skilled is on principal N. Among the 14 principals 12 are on the very highly skilled level while two (2) are on the highly skilled.

Test of Difference on the Level of Supervisory Skills of the Principals as Assessed by the Principals Themselves, the Teachers, and the Support Staff

The comparison of the assessment to the three groups of respondents namely, the principals themselves, the teachers, and support staff of the supervisory skills of the principals is shown in Table 14.

As shown in Table 14, the test of dissimilarity on the assessment of the three sets of participants on level of the supervisory skills of the principals. As confirmed by F values of six aspects of supervisory skills, none indicated a significant difference as tested at 95 % significance level.

Table 14. *Test of difference on the Supervisory Skills Level of S Principals as Assessed by the Principals Themselves, the Teachers and the Support Staff*

Supervisory Skills	F-value	p-level	Interpretation
A. Curriculum and Instructional Supervision	1.098	0.344	NS
B. Organization and Personnel Management	0.452	0.640	NS
C. Planning and Assessing and Reporting Teaching and Learning Outcomes	0.554	0.579	NS
D. School Plant, Resources and Facilities Management	0.678	0.514	NS
E. Personal, Social Growth and Professional Development	0.193	0.825	NS
F. School Community and Public Relations	0.33	0.719	NS

Significance is set at 0.05 probability level; Legend: NS = Not Significant

Therefore, it can be correctly declared that significant differences are not present on the supervisory skills of principals as assessed by the school principals themselves, faculty and the support staff on principals’ supervisory tasks of: curriculum and instructional supervision; organization and personnel management; planning, assessing and reporting teaching learning outcomes; school plant, resources and facilities management; personal, social growth and professional development; and school, community and public relations. Thus, the hypothesis that there are no significant differences on the assessment of the three sets of research participants on the level of the supervisory skills of principals in curriculum and instructional supervision, organization and personnel management, planning, assessing and reporting teaching learning outcomes, school plant, resources and facilities management, personal, social growth and professional development, and school and community relations is not rejected.

Relationship between the level of managerial competence and level of supervisory skills of the principals

Table 15 presents the relations on the level of managerial competence and the level of supervisory skills of the principals in the private secondary Catholic school in the cities in Eastern Visayas.

Table 15. *Relationship between the Level of Managerial Competence and Level of Supervisory Skills of the Principals of Catholic Secondary Schools in Eastern Visayas*

Level of Supervisory Skills	Level of Managerial Competence							
	Planning		Organizing		Leading		Controlling	
	r	p-level	r	p-level	r	p-level	r	p-level
A. Curriculum and Instructional Supervision	0.469	0.091	0.673	0.008	0.527	0.053	0.772	0.001
B. Organization and Personnel Management	0.705	0.005	0.629	0.016	0.570	0.033	0.722	0.005
C. Planning, Assessing, and Reporting Teaching Learning Outcomes	0.658	0.010	0.807	0.000	0.662	0.010	0.836	0.000
D. School Plant, Resources and Facilities Management	0.561	0.037	0.242	0.405	0.494	0.073	0.320	0.264
E. Personal, Social Growth and Development	0.630	0.016	0.726	0.003	0.720	0.004	0.825	0.000
F. School Community and Public Relations	0.616	0.019	0.772	0.002	0.612	0.020	0.772	0.001

Significance is set at 0.05 probability level

Looking at Table 15 above, four aspects of managerial competence are significantly correlated with five aspects of supervisory skills. Except for one aspect of the school principals supervisory skills, managerial competence in Planning is significantly related to Organizational and Personnel Management (r-value = 705, p-value = .005), Planning, Assessing, and Reporting Teaching Learning Outcomes (r-value = 658, p-value = .010), School Plant, Resources and Facilities Management (r-value = 561, p-value = .037), Personal, Social Growth and Development (r-value = .630, p-value = .016), and School Community and Public Relations (r-value = .616, p-value = .019).

=.019).

For Organizing as an aspect of managerial competence is significantly related to the supervisory skills in Organization and Personnel Management (r-value =.629, p-value = .016); Planning, Assessing, and Reporting Teaching Learning Outcomes (r-value =.726, p-value =.003); and School-Community and Public Relations (r-value = .772, p-value =.002).

Leading as managerial competence aspect is significantly related with Organization and Personnel Management (r-value = .570, p-value =.033); Planning, Assessing, and Reporting Teaching Learning Outcomes (r-value = .662, p-value = .010); Personal, Social Growth and Development (r-value =.720, p-value =.004); and School Community and Public Relations (r-value =.612, p-value =.020).

Management competence in Controlling is significantly related to five aspects of supervisory skills namely: Curriculum and Instructional Supervision (r-value =.772, p-value =.001), Organization and Personnel Management (r-value =.722, p-value =.005); Planning, Assessing, and Reporting Teaching Learning Outcomes (r-value =.836, p-value =.000); Personal, Social Growth and Professional Development (r-value =.825, p-value =.000); and School Community and Public Relations (r-value =.772, p-value =.001).

Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the management competence of the school principals in planning and their supervisory skills in organization and personnel management, planning, assessing, and reporting teaching learning outcomes, school plant, resources and facilities management, personal, social growth and professional development and school community and public relations is rejected; the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the management competence in organizing, leading and controlling and the supervisory skills in organization and personnel management, planning, assessing, and reporting teaching learning outcomes, personal, social growth and professional development and school and community and public relations is rejected.

The implication is when the level of the managerial competence of the principals is high the better is the supervisory skills they possess. Managerial Competence influences their supervisory skills as revealed in the findings. It denotes that the assessment of the teachers and the non-teaching personnel are consistent that the school principals in general are very highly competent in their managerial functions of planning, organizing, leading and controlling and are very highly skilled in their supervisory functions in curriculum and instructional supervision, organization and personnel management, planning assessing and reporting teaching learning outcomes, school plant, resources and facilities management, personal, social growth and professional development and school community linkages and public relations.

Problems Encountered by the School Principals along with their Managerial and Supervisory Functions

To determine the problems encountered by the school principals along with their managerial and supervisory functions, a one-on-one interview was done to the identified secondary school principals. The problems were classified according to the following themes: a) managerial problems, and b) supervisory problems.

To be able to classify as to whether the shared problems of the school heads in the private Catholic high schools in the cities of Eastern Visayas were managerial or supervisory in nature, it is necessary to distinguish the differences between managerial and supervisory functions.

The managerial and supervisory problems encountered by principals

This report summarizes the one-on-one interview with the school principals as part of the data gathering procedure in finding the managerial and supervisory problems encountered by the private school principals in Eastern Visayas as stated by the school principals themselves during the interview. The interviews were conducted in their respective schools were video recorded. The results of the interviews were classified into themes.

Theme 1: High Turnover of Teachers

A school principal cited the high turnover of teachers and the need to train new teachers, orient them to the tasks that they have to do. To be able to offer quality education school principals need to prepare these new teachers every beginning of the school year. If teachers stay longer then school principals can proceed to higher level of trainings, seminars and workshops to keep abreast with new trends of the secondary education.

Researcher: *“Good afternoon Ma’am. I am conducting a research which has something to do with school principals’ management functions and supervisory tasks. In this connection I am in need of your help. I need to know the problems encountered or experienced by the principals in their managerial and supervisory tasks. So may I know; what are some problems you encountered in managing and supervising the school?”*

School Principal 2: *“I have to cite one problem, I think on the part of the teacher especially that every year we have fast turn-over of teachers so every time we have to train them, orient them on the task that they do every year, every month...”* (SA2 Lines 42 – 45).

Similarly, another school principal expressed the difficulty of keeping the teachers longer in private schools. One principal said:

School Principal 3: *“..., of course there were problems in managing the school, one is from teachers, that is one, from private school*

to DepEd, we cannot compete with the compensation...we tell them to stay at least two years with us, it is your advantage because you have two years with us and you earned points.” (SA3, Lines 61 – 64).

Another school principal expressed that:

School Principal 13: *“If we have problem it is only because public school teachers are getting much higher pay than ours. Even if they want to stay but they are pressured by their family and I understand. Like now we have 27 teachers going out, we have more than a hundred teachers. Most of those who are going are new, working for us only for a year or after passing the licensure examination then they apply outside...”* (SA13, Lines 298-302).

These school principals considered high turnover of teachers a problem. They believed the longer the teachers stay in the school, the better are the relationship they can have with the students in the teaching-learning process.

Theme 2: Small Number of Enrollment

These school principals expressed their problem on how to keep the number of enrollment in their school. She considered it very necessary to keep the school afloat. At least two principals stated that:

School Principals 1: *“...small number of enrollment is one problem. It is a problem which I think shared by private schools, especially the small ones. It is a problem because it affects the schools sustainability because the financial resources is affected, thus, operational activities for improvement are limited.*

School Principal 8: *“...I have a challenge in terms of maintaining the number of students, since there are other schools who are offering the same strand or track with our school...”* (SA 8, Lines 175 - 177).

The decreasing trend of enrollment is a common problem of most private secondary schools especially the small ones. Many school principals shared the problem on the decreasing number of enrollment during meetings or conferences among private school principals during the Eastern Visayas Association of Private Schools (EVAPS) annual orientation usually done in the second month after the school opening.

The supervisory problems encountered by principals

Theme 3: Teachers’ insubordination/non-compliance of requirements

Some school principals cited insubordination of the some teachers as their problem or challenge. These were the common experiences of the school administrators who were promoted to the office of the principal. One principal stated that:

School Principal 9: *“...yes, problems like insubordination of some of the teachers, the non-compliance or resistance to comply with the requirements, they did not comply with submission of documents, particularly the year-end documents required by the school, habitual neglect of the teachers of their duties to attend meetings and assemblies, leaving their classes before time, so my last recourse was to ask help from the vice president of the academic affairs. I suppose they did that because they were my colleagues in the teaching profession before I was appointed to the position of a junior high school principal ...”* (SA 9, Lines 208-212).

Likewise, other school principals expressed that they found it hard to deal with some teachers.

School Principal 10: *“...there are problems/challenges I encountered since this is my first time as a principal, this time on how I am going to deal with some of the teachers especially that some of them were my teachers before some are my coordinators...”* (SA 10, Lines 226 - 227).

School Principal 6: *...the problems I encountered in this office includes, teachers who were not doing their job. I established honesty with teachers, I was open and straight in telling them about my assessment on their performance...* (SA 6, Lines 123-124 & 130 - 132).

Also a principal opined that absenteeism is a problem that she experienced as a school principal. She stated that not asking permission when one is going to be absent is a problem as it affects the students and their classes.

School Principal 4: *One problem is absenteeism of teachers without complying the agreement of asking permission from the office and leaving seatwork for students to do. And what can a principal do with that?* (SA 4, Lines 83-84).

Theme 4: Conflict among employees of diverse personalities

School principals consider conflicts among employees as a problem of administrators. Dealing with employees’ personal differences affect their relationship with co-workers which could lead to compromised performance. This was expressed by several principals:

Principal 1: *...managing conflict among people of diverse personalities is very crucial as well as dealing with jealousies among personnel ...* (SA 1, Lines 5-7).

Another school principal elucidated that:

Principal 5: *Yes there were, like differences of teachers, like seasoned and millennial teachers. They were given the same types of*

trainings, the same seminars, but in terms of owning the trainings by themselves, the seasoned teachers implemented what they learned better than the millennials, and it was because the seasoned teachers are more experienced. Another problem was the differences of ideas between these two groups. (SA 5, Lines 101 - 106).

One principal added that:

School principal 13: *“I do find some issues and challenges in this job because you manage different kinds of people, different kinds of persons with different personalities...”* (SA13, Lines 292 - 293).

Theme 5: Risk Management for the New Normal

One of the panel members suggested to include the managerial problems encountered by the school principals in making their respective schools ready for the new normal, hence we cannot deny that all of us who are working in schools are part of this problem hence there is a need for us to prepare. Like one principal said:

Principal 2: *“As to the preparation for the new normal, school conducted series of meetings with the top administrators. As the principal of the basic education department I and the assistant subject coordinators were tasked to prepare the program needed for the new normal. We started with the revising of the enrollment process-the online enrollment.”*

Another school principal was interviewed by the researcher through Messenger, since travelling during the height of COVID 19 Pandemic was highly discouraged. Applying the new normal norm, the researcher made use of distance interview/conferencing with the respondent.

Principal 13: *“For our preparation we conducted survey of our clients of their preferences of the different modes of the delivery the school proposed. Majority opted for blended, we will offer this. Since then, the teachers started preparing modules and others. We strengthened our previous safety protocols, our school medical team is doing it – upgrade safety protocols in our school.”*

“Some of the problems we experienced include: varied preferences of our clients regarding the delivery mode of the lessons- they are very much divided. The necessity to make adjustments in school fees. There are items which are no longer applicable like, spots fee, computer laboratory fee, medical-dental fee and others. Schedule of online classes so chaotic due to many things and situations to consider such as parents with three students with only one gadget/computer unit available, school budget as we anticipate substantial decrease of enrollment, employees transportation allowance when reporting to school for work and many other relevant problems.”

Another respondent was interviewed by the researcher through the use of face book messenger.

Principal 1: *“We conducted a survey through the use of goggle forms as to the availability of gadgets, on what forms students are comfortable to use for the forthcoming opening of classes. Meetings with the school head with other school administrators to plan and craft for the Continuity Plan. We conducted training for the teachers on the use of platforms for the opening of classes like google classroom. We attended webinars for online teaching. We assess the school with regards to internet connection capacity and upgrading.”*

“The problem we have is on the retooling of teachers and the various conditions especially the digital capacity of the learners.”

Another respondent answered the interview on the new normal.

School Principal 8: *“We get ready for the new normal through planning with the administrators, teaching, support staff and parents’ representatives. Part of the plan if the maximization of the use of internet and applications such as face book messenger, google classroom and email. We do have a better choice than to place the teaching-learning process in the digital world. This is a big leap from the traditional classroom setting we are all familiar with, bit my personal conviction is education must be fluid and should be ever evolving.”*

“The problems include unstable internet connection, some teachers whose ages are between 50 years old to 60 have difficulty in manipulating/using e-gadgets and the Learning Management System (LMS) or adopting the new set up – the on line learning, such as Zoom, google classroom ,messenger classroom, etc. One thing we discovered was we can easily connect the students through face book messenger than google classroom and other Learning management System (LMS) due to very shaky internet connections. We did try modular for the last 2 quarters of SY 2019-2020. The modules were delivered to a certain border where the teacher(s) and parents of our students met. Instructions were explained by the teachers to parents. If the student’s house is nearby the modules were delivered by the teachers to their houses and instructions were given direct to the students. The problem was on submission, some students cannot submit on the set time when teachers retrieved the modules from the agreed place where modules were delivered- this means teachers would go back to the place on other times to retrieve the work of those who failed to make it on the agreed date of retrieval. This was so taxing for the teachers.”

Another school principal shared how he/she prepared the school for the new normal and the problems they encountered;

School Principal 9: *“The preparations we did were: we conducted a survey as to how the school the school be ready to address the new normal situation we are having. We feel that there is a need to make learning continuity plan to serve as the blueprint of the*

school's operation for the forthcoming school year. We make frequent conduct administrative and academic meetings. We had General PTA Officers' meeting. Administrators, teachers and selected parents attended relevant online seminars.

As to the problems encountered, we did a dry run since we are still to continue the school year because we were only about to finish the third quarter when the suspension of classes was declared. To finish the term we did. The problems include unstable internet connection. It took long time before students pass the online class activities required, assignments, etc. again maybe because of poor signals and so they cannot connect to the internet. For the modular, we find it difficult to meet the target schedule for the distribution and retrieval of the printed materials. We found this so taxing for the teachers especially if in certain designated areas where a number of parents should meet with the teachers for submission and distribution for another module will not show up and sent a message that they will submit it a days later due to so many reasons. And to check the activities of the students one by one from modular then to online consumed a lot of time.

Generally, these problems of the principals were related to keeping teachers in the organizations and not transferring to government schools, the reduction of enrolment due to high school fees, teachers' behavior and attitudes of the teachers towards their superiors, and the inability of the schools to cope with the new normal caused the COVID 19 pandemic.

This study determined the principals' level of managerial competence and supervisory skills as perceived by 12 junior and 2 senior high school principals, 362 teachers and 65 non-teaching personnel in 12 Catholic schools in Eastern Visayas. The study employed mixed-method research design. A descriptive device - survey questionnaires in 2 parts were used to determine the level of managerial competence and supervisory skills of principals. The correlational design was to determine the relationship between the managerial competence and the supervisory skills of the principals. Analysis of Variance and Pearson Product Moment Correlation were used in the study. The study revealed that principals were very highly competent in their managerial functions and very highly skilled in their supervisory tasks. It further revealed that there was significant relationship between their levels of managerial competence and supervisory skills. For the qualitative data, the managerial challenges of the principals were on the small number of enrolment, high turnover of teachers, and the new normal challenge of COVID 19. On supervision, challenges include conflict among people of diverse personalities and insubordination and non-compliance of some teachers.

Conclusion

In the basis of the results of the investigations, these inferences were reached: The principals were generally very highly competent in performing their managerial functions of planning, organizing, leading, and controlling. There were no significant differences in the assessment of the three sets of research participants' as to the level of management competence of the principals. Generally, the skills of the principals on their role of supervision specifically in curriculum and instructional supervision, organization and personnel management, assessing and reporting teaching learning outcomes, school plant, resources and facilities management, personal, social growth and professional development, and school community linkages and public relations were very high. There was no a significant difference on the judgements of the three sets of respondents on the level of supervisory skills of principals. A significant correlation between level of managerial competence and supervisory skills of principals were present. It can be safely said in this study that when the managerial competence was high, the supervisory skills were also high. Based on the information gathered from video recorded one- on- one interview of the school principals, the problems they encountered along with their managerial function were: a) small number of enrollments, b) high turnover of teachers each year mainly because of the low teachers' remuneration/salary. On the supervisory tasks the mentioned problems were: a) conflict among people of diverse personalities; b) insubordination and or non-compliance of what were required of them. Another area to consider is the managerial competence of the school principal to manage the new normal challenges brought about by the COVID 19 Pandemic.

Grounded on the outcomes of this study and its conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed: The school head in coordination with School Planning Team (SPT) chaired by himself/herself may include in their school improvement plan (SIP) the following: Plan on how to increase the number of enrollment in each School Year, the principals may coordinate with the School Planning Team (SPT) together with the admission personnel and the committee on enrollment; coordinate with alumni officers and ask for suggestion on what to do to increase yearly enrollment; involve the parents' representatives and student leaders in planning on how to increase school enrollment, consider the result of the parents' satisfaction survey in planning.

School principals may recommend to the Board of Trustees to find ways to increase the teachers' remuneration which is the leading reasons of high turnover of teachers.

The office of the principal may craft or design relevant and updated conflict management program tailored for the teachers and support staff in coordination with the school guidance counselor's office to build a conflict free department.

The school principals exercised an open line communication between his/her office and the faculty and staff to iron out problems. This can be done through dialogue observing the protocol. Coordinate with the guidance counselor's office to conduct team building activities as part of the teachers' in- service training.

Conduct survey on parents and students as to the availability of electronic gadgets at home for the new normal and the parents' willingness to cooperate with and support their children with the kind of distant learning the school is capable to offer.

The school principal should be flexible to adopt to any given situation and be open to take some risks, like the new normal mode of delivering the lessons to the students.

A similar study may be conducted to include not only private Catholic schools but all private schools in the region regardless of ownership.

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